

Additional Data Help Desk Pro Tips an experienced Data Help Desk staffer!

After reviewing the [Volunteer Guidelines](#), here are a few other tips to help YOU help out at the Data Help Desk. My name is Wade Bishop, not only have I staffed several past Data Help Desks and evaluated them, but I was originally trained as a librarian and now teach people how to help others with information needs of all kinds as a Professor at the University of Tennessee iSchool (Bishop & Borden, 2021).

As an educator, I'll start with some basics from the Guidelines for Behavioral Performance of Reference and Information Service Providers 2023

(<https://www.ala.org/rusa/resources/guidelines/guidelinesbehavioral>). You can always read more, but the six key steps to providing good information services are:

- 1) Inclusion
- 2) Approachability
- 3) Engagement
- 4) Searching
- 5) Evaluation
- 6) Closure

The everyday meanings of these terms is enough to go on, but as you staff the Data Help Desk here are some ways to put them into action.

1) Inclusion means making sure service is as accessible as possible and to engage with people on their own terms and without assumptions. Across science conferences, many will have their own experiences, backgrounds, and differing terminology, meaning that helping others means taking a moment to understand each individual. Welcoming questions such as “Where do you work? What data do you work with?” are simple and help give you an understanding of the user’s perspective.

2) Approachability is key in any interpersonal communication as someone must feel comfortable asking you questions. To be approachable at the Data Help Desk, be visible, make eye contact, and ask “Have you heard of the Data Help Desk?” or “How may I help you?” or “Have you heard of ESIP?” If you direct your full attention to helping someone, using welcoming body language, or a simple greeting, this increases the likelihood of someone actually asking YOU a question.

3) Engagement! Users seldom start and end with the same question. When someone does not know something, their ambiguous query lacks the details to even properly ask it. So, the job of someone providing information assistance is to ask clarifying questions and express nonjudgemental interest. For example, you can ask probing questions like “Do you mean this

repository?” “What metadata standard are you using?” The most important factor for engagement is listening!

4) Searching means literally knowing where someone already looked, what terms they used, and any other ideas that would help YOU help THEM find what they are looking for. At the Data Help Desk, this may involve sharing your screen and demonstrating the search attempts for any data. The distinction in helping someone is that YOU are also teaching them how to search, where to start, how to frame a question, and all the while explaining why you are doing what you are doing. Sharing your approaches and search strategies will help all future searches for those new to data discovery.

5) Evaluation encompasses the fact that data literacy experts have to teach others how they evaluate data based on accuracy, authority, bias, coverage, credibility, currency, relevance, reliability, scope of information, and so forth. YOU may not have known you were an expert in all that until reading it, but YOU are and heuristics used to assess the quality of data are valuable skills. So, sharing your evaluation expertise with others is a real value of the Data Help Desk.

6) Closure. Good luck and goodbye! Wait, just kidding, that's no way to end any conversation. Closure at the Data Help Desk should include gathering some information from the user to keep in contact with them and encouraging them to reach out in the future if they have other data questions. You may refer them to other resources, individuals, and redirect them to their local librarians! The motto “I don't know everything, but I know where to find it” is a classic and the network of ESIP is massive. Closure is an ending to the current question, but leave everyone knowing that there is more help in the future when needed.

References

Bishop, B. W. & Borden, R. (2020). Scientists' Research Data Management Questions: Lessons Learned from Evaluations at a Data Help Desk. *portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 20(4), 677-692. [doi:10.1353/pla.2020.0032](https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2020.0032)

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